

Influence of Media in Incitement of Violence and its Effect on Student Education

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ABSTRACT

This study was aimed to pursue the avenue of influence of the media in inciting violence and other such negative emotions and their impact on the realm of education. This study was directed at one hundred and thirty student participants of different age groups, natives, and fields of study. All the students assessed, gave anonymous data with consent. The questionnaire was self-developed, approved by professors, and scores were indexed to percentage value. The findings of the study revealed that media did incite fear and violence through their content and hampered the emotional balance and educational experience of students with the same. The study also concluded that a governing body must be formulated to check content provided by the media.

Keywords: Anger, fear, Media violence, Education deterrents, Negative emotions

Media violence is one of the most heated debate topics amidst all class of people. It's evident from our day-to-day broadcast that all classes of people have been subjected to portrayal of violence by the media. Media has become a slaughterhouse of human emotions and a factory of manufacturing fear. The reason that makes media coverage, a toxin is the because the media doesn't filter their content for indiscreet negative coverage and violence. During its lifespan, the media often ends up reframing the story by emphasizing on different attributes of the event (Menield, Rose, Homa, & Cunningham, 2001). Evidence shows children imitate aggressive behavior. Researchers conducted a study on students happening in the mid 1990's in Israel. The focus of the study captured the effects of influence from children watching World Wrestling Federation (WWF) matches. The study revealed startling evidence demonstrating the students in the selected schools developed imitative behavior depicting what they say in the wrestling matches. The children practiced banging heads, throwing

opponents to the floor, jumping onto them from furniture, pulling hair and poking their eyes with fingers.

Contemporary research has concluded that violence is believed to stem up from extreme feelings like anger, depression, fear and helplessness. A study in 2014 by Justino Patricia, Marinella Leone, and Paola Salardi on the effects of violence on education, concluded that violence has both short- and long-term effects on the manner of education and affects the mental health of students. McGaha-Garnett (2010), an Assistant Professor of Applied Health and Educational Psychology at Oklahoma State University conducted another study to assess the impact of violence on classroom behavior and concluded that there existed a negative association between violence, academic progress,

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and appropriate classroom behavior. Students exposed to dysfunctional violent times were unlikely to have a positive outlook or behavior in classroom thus hampering education.

Andries (2011) appealed that “negative emotion is associated with cognition and it is in a dysfunctional way that individual’s became prone to negative thinking or keeping the processing of information towards undesired situation to be perceived in a threatening way” Gumora & Arsenio (2014) examined how emotional states are related to an individual’s cognitive and performance; they ended up finding out that students who experienced negative emotions had lower grade point average when compared to students who weren’t hampered by negative emotions.

Violence is one of the most profound of all the extreme feelings experienced by human beings. It is not present in a stable grounded emotional state of humans. That being said, it is actually very sensitive as it is incited or sparked by the smallest of things. A slight change of things, feelings or even circumstances can lead to devastating emotional surge of anger, depression or fear-which ultimately leads to intentional or unintentional violence.

Long terms of exposure to violence are detrimental not just in the physical scale but also affects the mental, physiological, psycho-social and economic scales of life too. Anger has been cited as an alarming reason for a range of cardiovascular and mental ailments. It is said to cause anxiety which in turn changes to self-harm or violence. High blood pressure arising out of anger or fear has reported to have created a spike in the occurrence of cardiovascular diseases and rendered many, lifeless. Repeated exposure to anger or violence can lead to insomnia and chronic headaches. Negative effects like anger and fear have evidently drawn students’ attention away from sound learning.

“Education is known as the stepping stone for every human activity” (Farooq *et al.* 2011). “An individual’s well-being and life opportunities are linked to their education, it guarantees the attainment of knowledge and skills that made it possible for an individual to have a better life” (Battle & Lewis, 2002). So, it’s highly important to plug those avenues that drain students away from good education and better mental health.

Media, the major chunk of the population undergoing education in India is youth (age 15-25). A survey study by Mr. Raj Vardhan (2021) led to a fact that the number of social media users in India were 376.1 million in 2020. This group of the population spends most of its time on indulging in different types of media. Media is used for a range of purposes by almost everyone. It’s an observation that students tend to look for inspiration, be it good or bad from the media. From an observers standpoint, it was found that media seemed to a certain degree, poison the viewers without being discrete about the violence they broadcast.

Media should function as a mode of communication and expression unlike manufacturing fear. The indiscretion and negligence of media in screening violence in their broadcast has led to students prone to extreme feelings like anger, depression, fear, trauma and has led to self-harm or other types of violence. The students face another issue of domestic violence, school violence or societal violence; where the inflictor gains disturbance from the viewed media. Here the student becomes a victim.

Being a student of education psychology, it was observed from my perspective that my peers and friends were acting differently or were inclined to anger after viewing violence in games and movies. This led me to search what affects the mental health of my peers. A slow observation throughout 2-3 weeks led me to believe that it might be the violence portrayed in the media itself. I tried playing some violent gun games and watching a violent movie. Unfortunately, I found it affecting my mental state too. This inspired me to take up this study and realize that violence incited by the media can be a dismembering factor in human lives and education.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Garcia, A.M.M. (2016). The role of positive and negative emotions to academic performance. Undergraduate Thesis Proposal, San Beda College.

The study was subjected on three hundred students of the San Beda college of all departments, courses and both genders. The results of the study pointed out that Considering the GPA of students, those with high academic potential had an influence of high amounts of positive emotions and had a meagre number of negative emotions. Meanwhile the few

who faced problems in excelling in academics had an influence of negative emotions more than the positive ones. The researcher inferred that, positive emotions might play a role in easing studies in addition to family, peers, communication and other factors. The researcher also explores the avenue that negative emotions might hinder a students' capabilities with its influence.

Objective of the study

- To gauge the media usage of the participants and to which type of violence they are subjected to.
- To identify what extreme feelings are induced by violence in media.
- To know whether the participants experience a change in behavior after being exposed to violence in media.
- To understand the effects from the above mentioned violence on education.

Hypothesis

Violence portrayed in the media does incite anger, fear and other such negative feelings that in turn affects the behavior and education of students.

Research Question

Are negative emotions incited by the violence in the media? If so, does it affect learning or education of an individual?

Research Method

Sample Space of the study

The study targeted individuals undergoing education and also individuals who are mature enough to introspect. The sample was 130 in number with students from both genders from different: schools, colleges, locality, natives and fields of study. The participants were asked of their consent to use the data provided for the terms of study. The participants are selected through Convenience Sampling. Convenience sampling is the method when the researcher made use of those who volunteer or willingly answer the questionnaire (Langham, 2007).

The questionnaire was prepared by deliberation with my professor in education, Professor Nandakumar

R, Regional Institute of Education-NCERT, Mysuru.. The questions were framed keeping in mind what are the most frequent questions that arise when media violence is discussed. To get a clearer picture, the questionnaire was prepared in three stages. One, understand an individual's access and usage of media. Two, to understand if an individual experiences violence in media, if yes what types. Three, how that violence seems to affect them and their education. These questions proved pivotal to the study and collection of data. All these questions arose as I went about asking myself what I felt like when I subjected myself to media violence. The questionnaire is attached in the Appendix A.

Procedure

All the participants were approached through either social media or personal contact. The participants were facilitated by an online questionnaire that was deliberated with peers and had 15 questions that met the objectives of the study. The data was collected in a span of a week and a half starting from 18th of June 2021.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

The study gathered data that a 44.9% of the participants indulged in media usage for more than five hours a day. The another 17.3% used media for more than 10 hours a day. This assured the fact that students do use the media for long amounts of time. 86.5% of the sample incline towards the idea that life cannot be lead without media. Though a strong 101% of the participants used the media for the purpose of entertainment, a strong 89% used media for academic purposes. This stands with my thought that media faces a multifaceted need. A key 74.8% of the participants found to be exposed to violence in the media. 61.1% of the sample space found anti-human elements portrayed while a healthy 54% and 53% were exposed to gruesome deaths and murders. Onto the negative effects, the participants experienced after the exposure to media violence; a baffling 60.2% experienced anger and a 61.2% experienced being helpless. A 57.1% percent of the sample and another 24.6% felt that their emotions were negated by violence in the media sometimes and always respectively. On the other hand, a total

of 60.2% felt that violence in the media molded their actions either sometimes unintentionally or intentionally. Does violence impede education? the prime question of the questionnaire actually gave a data of 53.1% agreeing that violence doesn't deter their education but a healthy 40.1% of the sample feels that the violence can deter and hamper their progress. When asked, whether it's easy to study with negative emotions, over 89.2% of them agreed that it's difficult or maybe difficult and a strong 91.3% of them agreed that a positive media can contribute constructively in realms of education. Over 57.3% agree completely that media is negligent and spreads violence and fear while another 28.2% are in neutral grounds of 'maybe'.

Statistical analysis

The collected data from the questionnaire was tabulated for better understanding and by using the frequency of the answers presented from the responses to the questionnaire, percentage value of the responses was calculated.

Table 1: The tabulated results of the questionnaire data

Attribute	Yes	Maybe	No
Acknowledgement of Violence in Media	74.8%	—	25.2%
Does media violence disturb the individual	24.6%	57.1%	18.3%
Are negative emotions triggered? (Anger, Fear)	60.2% avg	—	1%
Is Actions or thoughts affected by Media violence	60.2%	3.9%	35.9%
Are education tasks impeded by negative emotions	5.8%	35.9%	58.3%
Is learning difficult with negative emotions (anger, fear)	72.5%	16.7%	10.8%

Discussion

The result of the study yielded us with four breakthroughs. The results set us a foundation that majority of the participants have media as a vital part of their life and use it for a significant time in a day. Though the purposes varied, the usage was a major factor. A strong majority agreed to the fact that media employs violence in its broadcast. That stands with the objective of the study. The participants did find themselves in a pool of negative emotions. This concurrently supported my hypothesis that media incites negativity in the

participants. The thoughts and actions of a number of them were also affected by negative violence portrayed. Now onto the anomaly I found. While a strong percentage of the students agreed that they are experiencing negative thoughts after viewing violence in the media, they inclined to the idea that it did not hamper their studies. But on asking if they are in ease studying with negative emotions, most of them disagreed. That lands us to the fact that though students are affected in the realm of education through the negative thoughts incited by the violence in the media, they are reluctant to accept the same. This denial might be because of the need media proposes to our lives. The data now portrays that: 1. Media incites negative emotions when students are exposed to violence in the media. 2. Student education is hampered by the stirring of negative emotions that stem from violence in the media. From 1 and 2, we can infer that Media violence does hamper education by inciting negative emotions. Hence, the hypothesis is proved right and the purpose of the study seems fulfilled. The results don't confer that media violence affects education directly which seems parallel with yester studies and past publications but the results do establish that there is a link to media violence and hampering of education through incitement of violence. This disagrees with prior publications and studies.

Fig. 1: Usage of media

Fig. 2: Purpose of usage of media

Fig. 3: Individual discovery of violence in viewed media

Fig. 8: Does violence impede education?

Fig. 4: Types of violence found in viewed media

Fig. 9: Is learning easy with negative emotions?

Fig. 5: Negative feelings induced

Fig. 10: Is education better with positive media?

Fig. 6: Effect of viewed violence (1) {inciting negative emotions}

Fig. 11: Is media negligent and spreading violence and fear?

Fig. 7: Effect of viewed violence (2) {changes in actions or thoughts}

Fig. 12: Can life be led without media?

Fig. 13: Should media be governed?

CONCLUSIONS AND MEASURES

The study infers the conclusion that Media plays a multi-purpose need in student lives. Students are dependent on media for almost everything. Media employs violence in its broadcast which isn't discrete to the viewing audience. This violence in turn affects the viewing audience with inciting negative emotions like anger and fear. These negative emotions affect the thought process and actions of the viewing audience maybe intentionally or unintentionally. These negative emotions in turn affects education or the mindset towards education. Thus, hampering progress. In fact, studies infer that it doesn't just affect the students but also environments like home, school and workplace. It is agreed that the society has some anti-elements that the audience need to be aware of. The media needs to understand that creating awareness and spreading fear isn't the same thing. Media is a platform for communication and expression. Let it be used for the same instead of exploiting people's emotions for TRP and other ratings.

To adhere to the result found in this study, the following measures are suggested. There needs to be a strict governing media that makes sure that news and other media are screened for violence and is suitable for audience of all ages and sex.

Another measure that can be implemented is as follows, the media can have a separate section of violent media for people who believe they have a need to know about the violent elements too. Doing such a thing will protect the other sections of the audience that wants to stay away from violent elements of the media. Media needs to be kept away from control of a single person or an organization with ties to political parties and other agencies. This will make sure that the media agencies are accountable to the general public. People must be able to confront media when needed. Government needs to improve broadcast laws and take strict action against ones who breach such laws. This might curb violence to a large extent and keep the audience mentally healthy and reduce outbursts of violence in domestic, school, workplace and other areas of public interaction. In long terms of time this curbing can also lead to reduced crime rates, though that's a speculation, it is a possible outcome.

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